

Research Paper

Assessing the Community Leaders' Engagement in Reducing Land Encroachment Activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT: The study assesses the community leaders' engagement in reducing land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design; two research questions guided the study. The population of the study consisted of all 240 registered community development committee (CDC) leaders in the area. Total enumeration 240 CDC leaders was used in the study. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-structured questionnaire titled: Assessing Community Leaders Engagement in Reducing Land Encroachment Activities Questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha reliability method. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study proved that CDC leaders' engagement in promoting transparency and their engagement in conflict mediation enhances land encroachment activities in the Eleme local government area in Rivers State. Also, the null hypotheses were accepted. indicating that there is no significant in their engagement in promoting transparency conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities. It was recommended among others that government should train a group of community members in conflict resolution and mediation techniques.

Keywords: Land, encroachment, community engagement, conflict mediation, transparency.

I. Introduction

Land encroachment, which is one of the forms of communal conflicts that arise from deviations of interests, requirements, goals, values, and objectives in the competition for resources to meet the impressive demands of social life in a defined socio-physical environment. Conflict is a segment of human existence that should be evaded. It has been known to bring about outcomes that have a severe adverse effect on food production, peaceful co-existence, and economic development. A man in a socio-physical environment lives in a continuous process of dependence and interdependence, which often produces paradoxes and

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conflicts. (Bakare, & Moyo, 2022).) Land and its resources are very important to mankind as they provide a wide range of human needs. The needs, therefore, encroach on man to utilize land and its resources to satisfy his insatiable needs. Decisions concerning land utilization involve a complex mix of economic, political, and cultural purposes (Adeyanju,2021)). Land utilization, however, depends on who owns/controls a given plot of land, and also on the incentives and pressures that sharpen the land owner's behavior. Land encroachment as a phenomenon characterised by the large-scale acquisition of land by domestic or transnational companies, governments, or individuals, has emerged as a critical issue in the 21st century. This practice often displaces local communities, disrupts traditional livelihoods, and aggravates social and economic inequalities. In many parts of the world, particularly in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, land encroachment has become a significant threat to food security, environmental sustainability, and social cohesion. According to Borrás (2015), land encroachment involves the acquisition of land through various means, including purchase, lease, or concession, often without the free, prior, and informed consent of the affected persons, families, or communities. The drivers of land encroachment are multifaceted, including the global demand for food, biofuels, and minerals, as well as speculative investments in land as a financial asset (Fairbairn, 2015). The consequences of land encroachment are profound, leading to the displacement of rural communities, loss of biodiversity, and the erosion of traditional land tenure systems (Hall, 2015)

The participation of community leaders is a crucial solution to current problems towards a successful community by being the gateway to opportunities (Stiglitz & Kaldor (2017)). Community leaders are the vital force of communities straddling the outskirts. Consequently, it is these leaders' willingness, commitment, and degree of leadership that determine the success or failure of community development. Community leaders' promoting transparency, clarity, and accessibility of information, decision-making processes, and actions aid the success or failure of the community development. It involves being honest, accountable, and approachable in all interactions, ensuring that stakeholders have a clear understanding of what is happening and why. Transparency builds trust, promotes accountability, and enables informed decision-making. Community leaders serve as pivotal actors in mediating land-related conflict through culturally embedded dispute resolution mechanisms that effectively reduce land encroachment. (Adegbite, 2021). The persistence of land encroachment is a serious issue characterized by land racketeering, the involvement of armed groups, and the exploitation of weak land governance. While community leaders are central to managing land at the customary level, their roles are often undermined by corruption, lack of transparency, conflict mediation, and their frequent exclusion from formal land planning processes. The hurried urbanization and economic expansion in the communities in Eleme Local Government Area have deepened competition for land, generating a surge in illegal land encroachment and grabbing activities. Despite the existence of the Land Use Act, a persistent gap exists between statutory law and customary land management, often leaving local landowners vulnerable to displacement and exploitation by powerful actors using armed thugs or complicit officials. In this light, the researchers observed that the non-involvement of community leaders is one of the reasons for the poor reduction in land encroachment activities. This research aims to assess how community leaders can reduce land encroachment activities in communities in Eleme Local Government Area

II. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to assess the community leaders' engagement in reducing land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Examine the extent to which community development committee leaders' engagement in promoting transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria
2. Determine the extent to which community development committee leaders' engagement in conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

III. Research Question

1. To what extent does the engagement of male and female community development committee leaders in promoting transparency enhance the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria
2. To what extent does the engagement of male and female community development committee leaders in conflict mediation enhance the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

IV. Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study at a 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in promoting transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria

V. Literature Review

Kakatei, and Okoko (2023) Investigated on Community Leader and its Roles in Rural Development in Bayelsa and Rivers State, Nigeria. The study revealed that lack of infrastructural development in the rural areas, lack of a mechanized system to meet the modern trends of agricultural production, incessant high rate of corruption in governance, high rate of poverty to meet the necessities of life, amongst others, are the problems of underdevelopment in the rural areas in Bayelsa and Rivers State. Despite the above elements of underdevelopment listed above, in this regard, the study recommended that there should be synergy between the community leaders and development agencies that wish to embark on rural community development projects for effective execution, supervision, and sustainability of the projects and programmes. Disciplinary measures should be taken against community leaders and their representatives, and development agencies' representatives who are involved in embezzlement and misappropriation of funds, no matter whose ox is gored, to entrench transparency and accountability in rural development projects.

Jimoh, Mustapha, and Ojeifo (2020) Examined the Effects of Urban Encroachment on Rural Agricultural Land: A Case Study of Ibie-Nafe Community of Edo State, Nigeria. The findings show that the spreading of urban areas on farmlands causes new farmland reclamation and accelerated deforestation in the surroundings. In addition, the displaced farmlands do not ensure food production because of both reclaiming farmlands on infertile lands and diversifying farming activities from grain production to market-oriented ones. It implies that by the year 2030, agricultural and arable land, farmable land, and forest would have further been lost to urban encroachment. Erections of power lines were also identified as a major agent of change in the area due to the large Industrialization activities within the area, which have led to the loss of rural agriculture in the Ibie-Nafe Community.

VI. Methods

This study assesses the community leaders' engagement in reducing land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study was conducted in Eleme Local Government Area, Rivers State. The population of the study comprised all 240 male and female registered community development committee (CDC) leaders in Eleme Local Government Area, Rivers State (Rivers State Ministry of Chieftaincy and Local Government Affairs, 2026). The choice of using community development committee leaders was effective due to the

fact that they have local insight and understand the community's cultural context and language dynamics. Also, they witness land encroachment issues daily, which could enhance their responses. Total enumeration (240) was used for the sample size. Out of the ten communities in Eleme Local Government Area, a stratified sampling technique was adopted for the sample to select four (4) communities, namely: Akpajo, Aleto, Alesa, and Alode. These communities were explicated from the ten communities in Eleme Local Government Area, namely: Akpajo, Aleto, Alesa, Alode, Agbonchia, Ogale, Ebubu, Ekporo, Eteo, and Onne. Simple random sampling techniques was then applied to choose 60 community development committee (CDC) leaders in each of these communities (130 male and 110 female), making it a total of 240 community development committee leaders (CDC). The instrument for data collection was a self-structured instrument titled: Assessing Community Leaders' Engagement in Reducing Land Encroachment Activities Questionnaire (ACLERLEAQ). The instrument was designed using four (4) point rating scale from "Very High Extent" (1) to "Very Low Extent" (4). The research instrument was validated by two experts' judgment in the Measurement and Evaluation Department of the Educational Foundations Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. These experts assessed the questionnaire items for relevance, clarity, comprehensiveness, and appropriateness. The instrument was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha, conducted with data from the pilot study involving 40 respondents from the Elelewon community development committee leaders (CDC) in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, which is not part of the sample community. The reliability coefficient for the entire questionnaire was 0.90. A total of 240 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents at their meeting venue at the time that was communicated to the researchers through their respective heads. This was done with the aid of two research assistants; the copies of the questionnaires were retrieved immediately from the respondents. Out of the 240 copies of the questionnaire administered, 225 copies were successfully retrieved and used for analysis. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while t test was used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

VII. Results

1. To what extent does the engagement of male and female community development committee leaders in promoting transparency enhance the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 1. Mean Responses of male and female Community Development Committee Leaders' engagement on the extent to which Promoting Transparency enhances Land Encroachment Activities in Eleme Local Government Area Rivers State

S/N	Description	Male N = 116			Female N = 109		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1	CDC leaders use cultural values to educate community members about the importance of protecting communal land.	2.70	0.65	High Extent	2.65	0.58	High Extent
2.	CDC incorporates spiritual values in its efforts to protect communal land from grabbers.	2.62	0.61	High Extent	2.60	0.52	High Extent
3.	Community members respect traditional leaders' decisions regarding communal land due to their cultural and spiritual significance.	2.77	0.54	High Extent	2.69	0.67	High Extent
4.	Traditional leaders use ancestral lands and sacred sites as a basis for protecting communal land.	2.78	0.66	High Extent	2.70	1.20	High Extent
5.	Traditional leaders' cultural and spiritual roles influence community members' attitudes towards land grabbing.	2.85	0.72	High Extent	2.60	0.53	High Extent
6.	Community members are more likely to follow traditional leaders' guidance on land issues due to their spiritual authority.	2.75	0.69	High Extent	2.68	0.57	High Extent
7.	CDC leaders' use of cultural and spiritual values has been effective in reducing land encroachment activities.	2.88	0.76	High Extent	2.64	0.52	High Extent
	Grand Mean	2.76	0.66	High Extent	2.65	0.66	High Extent

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2026.

Table 1 above for the research question shows the mean responses of male and female Community Development Committee Leaders' engagement on the extent to which promoting transparency enhances land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area, Rivers State. Item 1 had mean scores of 2.70 and 2.65 with standard deviations of 0.65 and 0.58. Item 2 recorded mean scores of 2.62 and 2.60, with standard deviations of 0.61 and 0.52. Item 3 had mean scores of 2.77 and 2.69, with standard deviations of 0.54 and 0.67. Item 4 had mean scores of 2.78 and 2.70, with standard deviations of 0.66 and 1.20. Item 5 recorded mean scores of 2.85 and 2.60 with standard deviations of 0.72 and 0.53. Item 6 recorded mean scores of 2.75 and 2.68 with standard deviations of 0.69 and 0.57, while item 7 had mean scores of 2.88 and 2.64 with standard deviations of 0.76 and 0.52. The grand mean scores for both groups of respondents were **2.76** and **2.65**, respectively, both are higher than the decision mean. It therefore implies that both groups have a high extent that CDC leaders' engagement in promoting transparency enhances land encroachment activities in the Eleme local government area in Rivers State.

2. To what extent does the engagement of male and female community development committee leaders in conflict mediation enhance the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria?

Table 2. Mean Responses of male and female Community Development Committee Leaders' engagement on the extent to which conflict mediation enhances Land Encroachment Activities in Eleme Local Government Area, Rivers State

S/N	Description	Male			Female		
		N = 116			N = 109		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
8.	CDC leaders effectively resolve land disputes between community members.	2.70	1.22	High Extent	2.61	1.22	High Extent
9.	CDC leaders' mediation efforts reduce land encroachment activities.	2.78	1.18	High Extent	2.57	1.23	High Extent
10.	Community members trust CDC leaders to mediate land conflicts fairly.	2.86	1.13	High Extent	2.56	1.20	High Extent
11.	CDC leaders' efforts promote peaceful coexistence among community members.	2.60	1.24	High Extent	2.62	1.22	High Extent
12.	CDC leaders' mediation reduces community conflicts over land.	2.76	1.18	High Extent	2.65	1.24	High Extent
13.	CDC leaders collaborate with traditional rulers to resolve land encroachment.	2.71	1.19	High Extent	2.68	1.18	High Extent
	Grand Mean	2.74	1.19	High Extent	2.62	1.22	High Extent

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2026.

Table 2 above for research question 2 shows the mean responses of male and female Community Development Committee Leaders' engagement on the extent to which conflict mediation enhances land encroachment activities in Eleme Local Government Area, Rivers State. Item 8 had mean scores of 2.70 and 2.61, standard deviation of 1.22 and 1.22. Item 9 had mean scores of 2.78 and 2.57, standard deviation of 1.18 and 1.23. Item 10 had mean scores of 2.86 and 2.56, standard deviation of 1.13 and 1.20. Item 11 had mean scores of 2.60 and 2.62, standard deviation of 1.24 and 1.22. Item 12 had mean scores of 2.76 and 2.65, standard deviation of 1.18 and 1.24. while item 13 had mean scores of 2.71 and 2.68 with standard deviations of 1.19 and 1.18, respectively. The grand means of **2.74** and **2.62** were recorded. Both are higher than the criterion mean of 2.50, which indicates both are higher than the decision mean. It therefore implies that both groups have a high extent that CDC leaders' engagement in conflict mediation enhances land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government Area in Rivers State.

VIII. Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in promoting transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 3: t-test Analysis on the CDC Leaders' engagement on the extent to which Promoting Transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment Activities in Eleme LGA Rivers State.

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal.	t. crit	S/level	Decision
Male	116	2.76	0.66	223				
					1.01	1.96	0.05	Accept
Female	109	2.65	0.66					

Table 3 above shows the t-test analysis on how CDC Leaders' engagement in promoting transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme LGA, Rivers State. The t calculated value of (1.01) obtained is less than the t-crit value of 1.98. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. These imply that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in promoting transparency enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria

- There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 4: t-test Analysis on the CDC Leaders' engagement on the extent to which conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment Activities in Eleme LGA Rivers State.

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal.	t. crit	S/level	Decision
Male	116	2.74	1.19	223				
					0.82	1.96	0.05	Accept
Female	109	2.62	1.22					

Table 4 above shows the t-test analysis on how CDC Leaders' engagement in conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in Eleme LGA, Rivers State. The calculated value of t (0.82) obtained is less than the t-crit value of 1.98. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. These indicate that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities in the Eleme Local Government of Rivers State, Nigeria

IX. Discussion of Findings

The findings in research question 1, table 3 shows that CDC leaders engaged in promoting transparency in land encroachment activities in Eleme LGA OF Rivers State. Hence CDC leaders use cultural values to educate community members about the importance of protecting communal land, incorporate spiritual

values in their efforts to protect communal land from grabbers, community members respect traditional leaders' decisions regarding communal land due to their cultural and spiritual significance, traditional leaders use ancestral lands and sacred sites as a basis for protecting communal land, traditional leaders' cultural and spiritual roles influence community members' attitudes towards land encroachment, community members are more likely to follow traditional leaders' guidance on land issues due to their spiritual authority, and traditional leaders' use of cultural and spiritual values has been effective in reducing land encroachment activities. Corresponding hypothesis 1 confirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of CDC male and female leaders' engagement in promoting transparency in land encroachment activities in Eleme LGA of Rivers State. This finding affirmed the findings of Salami and Oyebade (2019) that CDC leaders ensure that land allocation is conducted fairly and transparently to ensure that no community member is being exploited, and ensure that community members' voices are heard in the related land use and management process. The finding is also related to the position of Briggs (2020) that leaders who insist on public witnessing and documentation of all land sales, and who maintain a public register of transactions, significantly reduce opportunities for clandestine, fraudulent deals. This transparency exposes and deters corrupt collaborations between community members and external actors.

The finding in research question 2, table 4, revealed that CDC leaders engaged in conflict mediation activities in Eleme LGA of Rivers State. This is evidenced in the grand mean of 2.74 and 2.62, which affirmed that CDC leaders effectively resolve land disputes between community members, traditional leaders' mediation efforts reduce land encroachment activities, community members trust traditional leaders to mediate land conflicts fairly, traditional leaders' efforts promote peaceful coexistence among community members, traditional leaders' mediation reduces community conflicts over land, CDC leaders collaborate with traditional ruler's to resolve land conflicts. Corresponding hypothesis 4 confirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on how conflict mediation engagement enhances land encroachment activities in Eleme LGA of Rivers State. The finding in research question 2 is in agreement with finding of Bolanle and Olayinka (2015) that conflict resolution strategies used by community elders and leaders of associations to resolve conflicts internally among residents in the housing estates include: Communication, mediation, negotiation, and reconciliation. The finding also corroborated with Nwoko, Okorobia, & Uchendu, (2020) that the traditional justice system, being more accessible and culturally resonant than the formal courts, provides a swift forum for resolving boundary and ownership conflicts. This rapid intervention prevents the violent confrontations that often characterise land encroachment and makes the community a less volatile target for encroachers. Agreeing with this, Ojo and Adebayo (2019) found that the restorative, rather than punitive, nature of traditional mediation often leads to more sustainable resolutions, healing community rifts that could otherwise be exploited by external interests. This implies that the conflict mediation capacity of traditional leaders is essential for de-escalating land-related disputes before they intensify.

X. Conclusion

The study assesses the community leader's engagement in reducing land encroachment activities in Eleme Local government Area of Rivers State. the variables of the study include promotion of transparency and conflict mediation. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that CDC leaders' engagement in promoting transparency and conflict mediation enhances land encroachment activities in the Eleme local government area in Rivers State. The null hypotheses were accepted, that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female community development committee leaders on the extent to which their engagement in promoting transparency and conflict mediation enhances the reduction of land encroachment activities.

XI. Recommendation

1. Community development committee leaders should create and implement rules to prevent encroachment and address violations and work with government agencies to enforce laws and regulations.

2. Government should train a group of community members in conflict resolution and mediation techniques and community development committee leaders should record mediation outcomes and ensure parties understand and respect the terms.

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